

Optical Inversion of the *cis*(NO₂), *trans*(N), *cis*(O)-bis(Aminocarboxylato)dinitrocobaltate(III) Ion**

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The inversion kinetics of optical isomers of *cis*(NO₂), *trans*(N), *cis*(O)-dinitrobis(aminocarboxylato)cobaltate(III) ions, containing various α - and β -amino acid residues (glycine, S-aminobutyric acid, S-leucine and β -alanine) have been studied. The inversion process was followed polarimetrically in sodium nitrate solution, between 55 and 95° (I=0.15). It was established that the inversion of the *cis*(NO₂), *trans*(N), *cis*(O) optical isomer of the dinitro-bis(β -alaninato)cobaltate(III) ion, in which β -alanine forms six-membered ring, is faster than the inversion of all other corresponding isomers containing five-membered aminocarboxylato ligand rings. In addition, it was assumed that the *cis*(NO₂), *trans*(N), *cis*(O) optical isomers of dinitrobis(aminocarboxylato)cobaltate(III) complexes containing α - and β -aminocarboxylato residues, respectively, rearrange via an intramolecular mechanism which involves the bond rupture between one end of the aminocarboxylato ligand and the central ion.

In our previous papers¹ the synthesis of several series of geometrical isomers of complexes of bis(aminocarboxylato) dinitrocobaltate(III) type, containing various α - and β -amino acid residues, respectively, were described. In another paper², we also reported the studies on the isomerization reactions of four geometrical isomers of the diglycinatodinitrocobaltate(III) ion (Fig. 1). The results of experiments between 65 and 95° in neutral solution are consistent with the stoichiometric mechanism:

In addition, we investigated³ the racemization of the isomer I, i.e. of (+)_{S,S}-*cis*(NO₂), *cis*(N), *cis*(O)-diglycinatodinitrocobaltate(III) ion.

Continuing these investigations, the inversion reactions of the optical isomers of *cis*(NO₂), *trans*(N), *cis*(O)-bis(aminocarboxylato) dinitrocobaltate(III) ions (IV) containing various α - and β -amino acid residues are described in the present communication. The inversion process was followed polarimetrically in sodium nitrate solution (I=0.15) between 55 and 95°.

Experimental

Preparation of the complexes:

All the investigated optical isomers were prepared as described earlier: glycinate (gly) complexes^{1,3}, β -alaninato (β -ala) enantiomers⁴, S-aminobutyrate (S-abu) diastereomers⁵ and S-leucinato (S-leu) diastereomers¹.

Fig. 1. The five geometric isomers of diglycinatodinitrocobaltate(III) ion. Isomers I-IV have been isolated. Isomer V has not been observed.

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Kinetic experiments :

Inversion reactions were studied by heating 0.5 cm³ of aqueous solutions (having a concentration of 0.05 mol/dm³) of the corresponding enantiomer or diastereomer, in glass ampules placed in an ultrathermostat (Thermostat Type NBE, Medingen, Dresden). Since paper chromatographic studies had shown that the (-)-*cis*(NO₂)-*trans*(N)-*cis*(O)-enantiomer of dinitrobis(β-alaninato)cobaltate(III) ion is partially decomposed at temperatures above 80°, the corresponding kinetic racemization experiments were carried out at 55, 65, 75 and 80°, respectively. The ionic strength was 0.15, adjusted with sodium nitrate. In course of the kinetic experiments the ampules were taken out from the thermostat at given time intervals and quickly cooled in ice water. Solutions from the ampules were quantitatively transferred into a 10 cm³ volumetric flask, which was then filled up to the mark with distilled water. Optical rotations of the solutions obtained were measured in a Perkin Elmer 141 MC Digital Polarimeter at sodium line (±0.002°).

In each experiment, it was checked whether the substance studied had either partially decomposed or isomerized in course of heating at the above mentioned temperatures. This was accomplished by paper chromatographing the heated solutions or by taking their visible spectra; the R_f values as well as the electronic spectra thus obtained were compared with those obtained with the samples of substances which had not been heated.

Evaluation of the kinetic parameters :

In case of a reversible first order reaction

the change of concentration of the component B with time is given by the equation :

$$[B] = [\bar{B}] / (1 + e^{-(k_1+k_{-1})t}) \quad \dots (1)$$

where [B] denotes the concentration of the component B, and $\bar{B}$ its equilibrium concentration⁶.

Expanding e^{-(k₁+k₋₁)t} as a power series, gives :

$$[B] = [\bar{B}] \left\{ \frac{(k_1+k_{-1})t}{1!} - \frac{(k_1+k_{-1})^2 t^2}{2!} + \dots \right\} \quad \dots (2)$$

Dividing the equation (2) with t the following is obtained :

$$\frac{[B]}{t} = [\bar{B}] \left\{ \frac{(k_1+k_{-1})}{1!} - \frac{(k_1+k_{-1})^2 t}{2!} + \dots \right\} \quad \dots (3)$$

The above equation shows that the graphic representation of $\frac{[B]}{t}$ (the ordinate) as a function of t (the abscissa) in the beginning of the reaction, i.e. when in the equation (3) all the members except the first

two can be neglected, gives a straight line with the intercept $[\bar{B}](k_1+k_{-1})$ and the slope $-\frac{[\bar{B}](k_1+k_{-1})^2}{2}$.

This procedure is analogous to that for irreversible first order reactions described by Hall *et al*⁷.

$$\text{Since } [\bar{A}] + [\bar{B}] = [A_0] \quad \dots (4)$$

(where [A₀] denotes the initial concentration of the component A), and

$$\frac{[\bar{B}]}{[\bar{A}]} = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} = K \quad \dots (5)$$

it follows that from the data obtained by the procedure described, k₁, k₋₁ and $\bar{B}$ can be calculated in the following manner :

$$k_1 = \frac{\text{intercept}}{[A_0]} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$k_{-1} = -\frac{2(\text{slope})}{\text{intercept}} - k_1 \quad \dots (7)$$

$$[\bar{B}] = -\frac{(\text{intercept})^2}{2(\text{slope})} \quad \dots (8)$$

The change in the concentration of the component B with time in course of the reaction was determined in the usual way by measuring the optical rotation of the solutions :

$$[B] = [A_0] \frac{(\alpha_A - \alpha_t)}{(\alpha_A - \alpha_B)} \quad \dots (9)$$

where α_A and α_B denote the optical rotations of the solutions of pure A and B components, respectively, and α_t is the optical rotation of the investigated solution in course of the reaction.

Chromatographic investigations :

Paper chromatography of the investigated substances was carried out in a glass cylinder, height 50 cm, diameter 22 cm, by ascending method, on Whatman No. 1 paper strips (3×30 cm). The development was performed at 20±2°, the solvent system being placed into the cylinder 1 hr before development. The solvent system used was a mixture of ethyl acetate : ethanol : water (70 : 20 : 10). The solvent front travelled about 22 cm and the developing time was about 6 hr. The substances were detected by dipping the developed paper strips into ammonium sulphide solution (~2 mol/dm³).

Absorption spectra :

Absorption spectra of the investigated substances in the visible region were taken in aqueous solutions on a Perkin Elmer 137-UV spectrophotometer.

Optical rotation :

Optical rotation of the isomers obtained was measured at 589 nm on a Franz Schmidt & Haensch Model S Polarimeter; the measurements were performed at room temperature in 10 cm³ cells with aqueous solutions, the concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 0.2 g per 100 cm³.

Reagents :

All reagents used were of "puriss" reagent grade purity. Sodium hexanitrocobaltate(III) was a product of E. Merck, AG, Darmstadt, or Fluka AG, Buchs. S-Aminobutyric acid and S-leucine were the products of Fluka AG, Buchs, whereas glycine and β -alanine were obtained from Kemika, Zagreb.

Results and Discussion

The observed first order rate constants are given in Table 1, and the corresponding activation enthalpies and entropies in Table 2 (see also Fig. 2 and 3).

($\Delta S_{75}^{\ddagger} = -64.1 \text{ k cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) but that is not the case with the other isomer ($\Delta S_{75}^{\ddagger} = -13.3$ to $3.91 \text{ k cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). On the basis of these, one can conclude that the inversion mechanisms of the two isomers are different. As is known⁸, an intramolecular mechanism without bond rupture, the trigonal twist mechanism, might account for the low enthalpy and the highly negative entropy of activation. Because of this, we assumed in our earlier paper² such a mechanism for the racemization process of the *cis,cis,cis*-isomer. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that an examination of the stereochemistry of the two investigated isomers reveals that the *cis,cis,cis*-isomer can theoretically racemize by

 TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER INVERSION RATE CONSTANTS ($k_{\text{inv}} \cdot 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$) OF OPTICAL ISOMERS OF *cis*(NO₂),*trans*(N), *cis*(O)-*bis*(AMINOCARBOXYLATO)DINITROCOBALTATE(III) ION*

Complex	Temperature (°C)											
	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ gly ₂] ⁻	-	-	-	-	1.3±0.1	2.8±0.2	3.5±0.2	11±1	15±1	-	62±6	-
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-abu) ₂] ⁻	-	-	-	-	-	2.1±0.5	-	5.4±0.2	-	14±1	-	43±1
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-leu) ₂] ⁻	-	-	-	-	-	2.1±0.5	-	5.5±0.3	-	15±1	-	47±1
$\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-abu) ₂] ⁻	-	-	-	-	-	1.8±0.5	-	4.8±0.6	-	12±1	-	36±1
$\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-leu) ₂] ⁻	-	-	-	-	-	1.0±0.4	-	3.1±0.3	-	7.7±0.2	-	21±1
$\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (β -ala) ₂] ⁻	-	-	-	14±2	-	30±3	-	70±4	120±20	-	-	-
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ - <i>cis, cis, cis</i> -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ gly ₂] ⁻	120±5	140±10	150±5	170±10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

* The observed rate constants are given in the form of $X \pm t(P; f) \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$, where X represents their mean values obtained by the least squares method, $t(P; f)$ is student's factor for P=95%, f=n-2 degrees of freedom and $\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$ standard deviation of the mean (J. M. Wilson *et al*, Experiments in Physical Chemistry, II Ed., Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1968, p. 364).

 TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF INVERSION REACTIONS OF OPTICAL ISOMERS OF *cis*(NO₂),*trans*(N),*cis*(O)-*bis*(AMINOCARBOXYLATO)DINITROCOBALTATE(III) ION

Complex	$\Delta H^{\ddagger}$ k cal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S_{75}^{\ddagger}$ k cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ gly ₂] ⁻	29.7	3.91
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-abu) ₂] ⁻	24.0	-11.9
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-leu) ₂] ⁻	24.6	-10.1
$\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-abu) ₂] ⁻	23.6	-13.3
$\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (S-leu) ₂] ⁻	24.4	-11.8
$\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀ -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ (β -ala) ₂] ⁻	18.5	-24.6
$\Lambda(+)$ ₅₀₀ - <i>cis, cis, cis</i> -[Co(NO ₂) ₃ gly ₂] ⁻	3.87	-64.1 ^a

^a For 45°

 Fig. 2. A typical plot of $\log \alpha$ vs time [obtained during the racemization of $\Delta(-)$ ₅₀₀-*cis*(NO₂),*trans*(N), *cis*(O)-*bis*(β -alaninato)dinitrocobaltate(III) ion].

It can be seen from these data that the inversion rate of *cis, cis, cis*-isomer is very much greater than that of the *cis*(NO₂),*trans*(N),*cis*(O)-isomer. This is in accordance with the rather low activation enthalpy of the former isomer, which amounts to 3.87 k cal mol⁻¹ [the corresponding values for the *cis*(NO₂), *trans*(N), *cis*(O)-complexes, which also contain α -aminocarboxylato ligands, are between 23.6 to 29.7 k cal mol⁻¹]. In addition, the *cis, cis, cis*-isomer has a highly negative activation entropy

a trigonal twist whereas the inversion of the *cis*(NO₂),*trans*(N),*cis*(O)-isomer by a twist mechanism is not possible.

From the data obtained it can also be seen that the optical inversion of the *cis*(NO₂),*trans*(N),*cis*(O)-complex containing β -alaninato ligands is considerably faster in comparison to the complexes

Fig. 3. A typical plot of $\log k$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$ [obtained for racemization process of $\Delta(-)_{899}$ -*cis*(NO₂)-*trans*(N)-*cis*(O)-*bis*(β -alaninato)dinitrocobaltate(III) ion].

of the same geometrical configuration containing α -aminocarboxylato ligands. This is in accordance with its relatively lower activation enthalpy, as well as with the known fact⁹ about greater stability of five-membered rings in comparison to six-membered ones. On the basis of this one could assume that the optical inversion of the investigated complexes takes place by bond rupture between aminocarboxylato ligand and Co(III). It is, however, unlikely that during this process a complete chelate ligand dissociation occurs because of relatively modest activation enthalpies (not higher than 30 k cal mol⁻¹). In addition, if such a complete dissociation happens a noticeable complex decomposition would be expected. That was never observed. In this connection, it seems more probable that under the labilising influence of the *trans* NO₂-group, the Co-O bond is broken rather than the Co-N bond (from aminocarboxylato ligand).

The assumed bond rupture intramolecular mechanism is supported by the fact that the activation energy for the substitution process of the NO₂-groups in hexanitrocobaltate(III) ion by aminocarboxylato ligand, for which reaction a dissociation mechanism is accepted, amounts to about 37 k cal

mol⁻¹, which is a much higher value compared to the values obtained in the present study. Finally, the proposed mechanism is also in accordance with the results obtained by York¹¹, who established that an exchange involving ¹⁵NO₂⁻ and *cis*-Na[Co(acac)₂(NO₂)₂] is extremely slow.

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